
Geographical Study of Landuse Efficiency in Sangli District (Maharashtra)

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Abstract:

Landuse refers to how people use the land, including the economic and cultural activities that take place on it. Cropping intensity is a ratio between gross cropped area and net sown area in a component areal unit. The Sangli district is one of the southernmost district of Maharashtra State. The present research paper is giving emphasis on the landuse and cropping intensity of the study region. Study is based on secondary source of data which is collected from district socio economic abstract of Sangli district. The study of landuse pattern in the study region is classified into five categories i.e. Area under Forest, Area not Available for Cultivation, Other Uncultivable Land, Fallow Land and Net Sown Area. The net sown area is significant in the study area basically riverside fertile plains region has more area under cultivation. Cropping intensity is high in tehsils where well-developed irrigation facilities and fertile black soil.

Introduction:

The concept of landuse is related to the use of which land is put in a certain reason at a given period of time. Landuse is related to conservation of land from one major use to another general use (Nanvati, 1951). Changing man - environment relationship also play an important role in defining the landuse of a particular region. The basic objective of landuse pattern is to utilize the limited available land. Landuse patterns are complex and dynamic. Landuse analysis shows the status of land utilization for different purpose in an area.

Landuse efficiency can be defined as the extent of net sown area. The gross cropped area as percentage to the net area sown provides a measure of landuse efficiency which means cropping intensity and represents the number of crops grown on the same area in only one agricultural year (Singh, 1972). The main objective of landuse efficiency is to examine the regional

differences in agricultural efficiency of the study area.

Objectives:

The main objective of the present work is to highlight and assess the landuse pattern and landuse efficiency of the Sangli district.

Data Collection And Methodology:

Present study is generally depends on the secondary source of data which is collected from socio-economic abstract of Sangli district 2023-24. The collected secondary data has been processed, tabulated and interpreted. The landuse efficiency is calculated by using the following formula –

$$\text{Landuse Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Gross Cropped Area}}{\text{Net Sown Area}} \times 100$$

Statistic techniques such as mean and standard deviation has been used for the categories of low, moderate and high cropping intensity area of the study region

in. On the basis of these statistical techniques result and conclusion are drawn.

Study Area:

The Sangli district is one of the district of Maharashtra state and situated between the latitude of 16°43' North and 17°38' North and the longitude of 73°41' East and 75°41' East. It is bounded by the Satara district on the north western side, southern part is bounded by Belgaum and Bijapur district of Karnataka state and Ratnagiri and Kolhapur district lies on the western part of Sangli district.

Fig. 1

Table No. 1: Tehsil Wise Land Use Pattern in Sangli District: 2023 - 24 (Area in Percent)

Tahsil	Geographical Area	Area Under Forest	Area Not Available For Cultivation	Other Uncultivable Land	Fallow Land	Net Sown Area
Shirala	63417	30.32	18.21	0	4.57	46.90
Walwa	84567	11.72	10.50	1.46	2.48	73.84
Palus	24436	0	11.34	0	3.30	85.36
Kadegaon	58056	7.68	16.11	0	7.51	68.70
Khanapur	72725	15.13	20.26	2.97	4.90	56.74
Atpadi	85654	1.80	18.25	14.53	19.77	45.65
Tasgaon	79866	5.30	16.53	0	4.68	73.49
Miraj	92102	2.21	16.72	1.44	6.61	73.02
K. Mahankal	73489	2.52	13.07	11.75	15.50	57.16
Jath	224538	5.85	4.76	2.97	5.24	81.18
District	8,58,850	7.52	12.65	3.76	7.26	68.81

Source: Computed by researcher based on Socio-Economic Abstract of Sangli District, 2023-24

Table No. 1 shows the landuse pattern of the study region. Total geographical area of the study region is

The study region covers an area of 8,572 sq. km. of supporting 28, 20,575 population according to 2011 census. Administratively it consist of ten tehsils Viz., Shirala, Walwa, Palus, Kadegaon, Khanapur, Atpadi, Tasgaon, Miraj, Kavathemahankal, and Jath. The region receives rainfall mainly from south-west monsoon. Sangli district has a well-developed drainage pattern by Krishna, Warna, Yerala, Agrani, Nanni and Bor.

Landuse Pattern:

The concept of landuse is relates to the use of land that is used for specific activities over a period of time. A landuse study is of great importance as it can give a picture of the intensively used and unused land of an area.

8,58,850 hectare. The proportion of area under forest is 7.52 percent to the total geographical area of the region. Out of total

geographical area 12.65 per cent area is not available for cultivation which is covered by industries, settlement and transport network. The proportion of area under fallow land is 7.26 percent while area under agriculture is 68.81 percent of the total geographical area of the study region.

Area under Forest:

The western part of Sangli district is covered by Sahyadri hilly region and therefore densely forested. About 7.52 percent of the area in the district is covered by forest. The tehsil-wise distribution of forests shows variation. The Shirala tehsil cover highest percent of forest with 30.32 percent and followed by Khanapur and Walwa tehsils. In general forest cover is decreased from western part to eastern part the study region because eastern part of Sangli district is drought prone region.

Area not available for cultivation:

Land under non-agricultural uses, barren and uncultivable land is included in this group. Area under non-agricultural uses includes land occupied by road, water bodies, buildings and railway network etc. The average proportion of such land in study region is 12.65 percent. Highest proportion is observed in Khanapur (20.26 percent) tehsil and lowest was in Jath tehsil with 4.76 percent.

Other Uncultivable Land:

This group includes permanent pastures, land under tree crops, cultivable wastelands and broken grounds. In the study area average proportion of such land is 3.76 percent. Highest proportion of other uncultivable land is observed in Atpadi tehsil with 14.53 percent and lowest was in

Shirala, Palus, Kadegaon and Tasgaon tehsils.

Fallow Land:

Fallow land is land that is not under cultivation at present but it was under cultivation in the past. It can be divided into two groups which are current fallow and permanent fallow land. In study area average 7.26 percent fallow land has been found. Highest proportion of fallow land is found in Atpadi tehsil with 19.77 percent whereas lowest proportion of fallow land is observed in Walwa tehsil with 2.48 percent.

Net Sown Area:

The land which is actually under crops in the current year is called as net sown area. About 68.81 percent of the land is under various crops in the study area. The highest proportion of net sown area is found in Palus tehsil with 85.36 percent due to availability of water and fertile soils. Lowest proportion is observed in Shirala tehsil (46.90 percent) due western part of Sangli district is hilly region.

Landuse Efficiency:

Cropping intensity refers to number of times crops are grown and harvested on a given area of land within a year. This can be calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Landuse Efficiency} = \frac{\text{Gross Cropped Area}}{\text{Net Sown Area}} \times 100$$

Gross cropped area is the total area sown once or more than once in a year. Net sown area is the total area sown including crops and orchards, counting the area sown more than once in the same year only once. Table No. 2 shows tehsil wise cropping intensity of the study region in 2023 - 24.

Table No. 2: Tehsil Wise Landuse Efficiency in Sangli District: 2023 - 24 (Area in hectare)

Tahsil	Gross Cropped Area	Net sown Area	Cropping IntensityPercent
Shirala	38100.5	20300.5	187.68
Walwa	72946.82	70128.82	104.02
Palus	26561	21678	122.53
Kadegaon	47541.65	28949.65	164.22
Khanapur	38383.75	28828.75	133.14
Atpadi	35282.35	31861.15	110.74
Tasgaon	61334.7	49162.7	124.76
Miraj	75814.15	55942.46	135.52
Kavatthe Mahankal	47628.6	36072.6	132.04
Jath	181230.22	156817.22	115.57
District	624823.74	499741.85	125.03
		Mean	133.02
		SD	24.06

Source: Computed by researcher based on Socio-Economic Abstract of Sangli District, 2023-24

Table No. 3: Sangli District: Area of Landuse Efficiency (2023 - 24)

Category	Intensity Value	Name of Tehsils
Area of High Efficiency	Above 157.08 %	Shirala, Kadegaon
Area of Moderate Efficiency	108.96 % to 157.08 %	Miraj, Khanapur, Kavathe Mahankal, Tasgaon, Palus, Jath, Atpadi
Area of Low Efficiency	Below 108.96 %	Walwa

Source: Computed by researcher based on Socio-Economic Abstract of Sangli District, 2023-24

Area of Low Efficiency (Below 108.96 %):

Area of low efficiency is distributed in Walwa tehsil with 108.96 percent. Because Walwa tehsil are located in river basin area therefore there are fertile black soil, high availability of water for irrigation and relatively high amount of rainfall received resulted in high cultivation of cash crop like sugarcane. As the area under sugarcane crop is more, the gross cropped area is less as compare to other tehsils and hence low cropping intensity.

Fig. 2

Area of Moderate Efficiency (108.96 % to 157.08 %):

Areas of moderate efficiency are confined to Miraj (135.52 percent), Khanapur (133.14 percent), Kavathe Mahankal (132.04 percent), Tasgaon (124.76 percent), Palus (122.53 percent), Jath (115.57 percent) and Atpadi (110.74 percent) tehsils. All these tehsils has medium developed of irrigation facilities, grey, medium to black soil, some part of these tahsils are hilly region, other natural as well as socio economic factors resulted low cultivation annual crop like sugarcane therefore leads to high cultivation of other crops.

Area of High Efficiency (Above 157.08 %):

High efficiency observed in Shirala tahsil with 187.68% because there having shallow red soil, heavy rainfall as well as raise of irrigation which suitable for rice, soybean also summer groundnut cultivation. In Kadegaon tehsil because of fertile black soils and well developed irrigation facility as

well as the developed agricultural techniques of this region gives high efficiency with 164.22 percent.

Conclusion:

The area under forest in the study area is observed with 7.52 percent, it needs to be increased in the forest. The net sown area is significant in the study area basically riverside fertile plains region has more area under cultivation. Area not available for cultivation is covered by industries, settlement and transport network. The area under fallow is higher in eastern part of the study region whereas the area under agriculture is higher in central and western part of the district. Landuse efficiency is high in Shirala and Kadegaon tehsils because of well-developed irrigation facilities and fertile black soil. Moderate efficiency is in Miraj Khanapur, Kavathe Mahankal, Tasgaon, Palus, Jath and Atpadi tehsils of Sangli district. Walwa tehsil located in river basin area, fertile black soil and high availability of water resulted in high cultivation of sugarcane hence the gross cropped area is low.

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